

THE ROLE OF THE COMPUTER IN THE TRANSLATION PROCESS

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Abstract. *Translators and interpreters use computers, online dictionaries and terminological databases, automatic machine translation tools, search engines, various communication tools and other types of ICT in their daily work. The issue of the use of Internet translation technologies and machine translation tools has been the cause of controversial discussions. They explained that the use of electronic devices, online translators and CAT, in their opinion, do not allow students to develop good translation skills.*

Keywords: *translators, text, CAT, ICT, electronic structure, online translators, translation technologies, terminological data, automatic machine, search structures, translation tools, internet, text, speech.*

Currently, information and communication technologies (ICT) are part of both interpreting and translation activities, and most professionals in this field use ICT in their work. Translators and interpreters use computers, online dictionaries and terminological databases, automatic machine translation tools, search engines, various communication tools and other types of ICT in their daily work. Therefore, Bachelor of Translation Theory and Practice curricula should include ICT-based elements to provide students with an appropriate learning experience. In order to prepare for the real professional world, graduates need not only language knowledge and skills, but also ICT skills, and some experience in using modern electronic means of translation and translation. In addition, ICT needs to be integrated into the entire educational process to make it more effective and practice-oriented.

Graduates are expected to have linguistics, mainly translation studies, knowledge of professional terms in their native and native languages, translation and interpreting skills, strong communication skills, and the ability to work in the international community. In our opinion, the integration of ICT into the curriculum helps to achieve the goal of training qualified translators.

Translators ICT is mainly used to provide relevant texts in different languages for translation practice, as well as to provide students with modern tools such as CAT (Computer Assisted Translation) for translation and translation support: online dictionaries, glossaries and databases, search engines, communication tools, etc.

The issue of the use of Internet translation technologies and machine translation tools has been the cause of controversial discussions. Many teachers oppose the use of these technologies in translation classes and independent research. They emphasize the need to teach students to translate correctly using their mind, memory, cognitive abilities and skills, as well as dictionaries. They explained that the use of electronic devices, online translators and CAT, in their opinion, do not allow students to develop good translation skills.

But the undeniable fact is that the rapid development of online translation tools like GoogleTranslate has already changed the whole world. Nowadays, almost everyone who uses foreign languages, for example, a translator, also uses these tools. Thus, it seems unreasonable to ban these technologies in the classroom, since students use them in their practice anyway. We

sometimes recommend linking to these tools to help students get the most out of them. For example, training with online translation tools (Google Translate and its Translator, Translator) will inform students about the possibilities and limitations of machine translation. According to the American researcher K. Beer, such activities help students "feel the similarities and differences between their native language and the language they are translating", which is undoubtedly useful for future translators. is considered. Online resources also provide audio and video materials ideal for developing translation skills. It is recommended to use notes instead of reading or speaking for translation exercises among students, because the teacher should be able to listen to the students' speech, observe and correct possible mistakes or shortcomings in pronunciation. At the end of your serial translator studies, I recommend dailies to develop your translation skills. It is also worth noting the self-study of serial translators - today there are video lessons for TL, video and audio, texts for translation, repositories of speeches, as well as exercises for teaching translation shorthand. There are a number of websites that include Examples of such sites are: <http://interpreters.free.fr/consec.htm>; <http://interpreters.free.fr/simultaneous.htm>; <http://www.orcit.eu/resources-shelf-en/story.htm>. Video-Library. Based on the current teaching experience, it can be concluded that the use of information available in such Internet resources allows students to independently prepare the necessary texts. In professional translation circles, the experience of A. Drekzel, a translator working in various European organizations, is attracting interest, he actively introduces various information technologies and applications for Android and Apple into translation practice.

In particular, it uses the iPad as a mobile data carrier for quick access to a reference or term base during translation, as well as a digital notepad for translating notes using a stylus. - Readdle Documents, Clean File Manager file managers allow you to efficiently organize work files and synchronize them between mobile devices;

– virtual scanners Scanbot, Scanner Pro (and others), which allow you to use the internal tablet camera to digitize documents. Multifunctional electronic notepads Note Shelf, Notability, Bamboo Paper, with the help of which recording of translation is carried out. ICT skills and the ability to use them in their work are an integral part of translation competence, that is, they are part of the translator's information competence. It is necessary to use ICT in the preparation and execution of exercises for teaching SP, because teachers need to use Internet resources to search for different types of real texts, necessary audio recordings, etc., students need to use online dictionaries and independent learning resources. In the process of organizing PPD training, it is necessary to follow the set goals by performing exercises. The goal of our methodology is the formation of the translation competence of sequential translation, therefore, the set of exercises used in the educational process is necessary to develop and improve all components of this competence. When teaching PPD through exercises, it is necessary to follow the set goals that are achieved by performing exercises in the process of organizing PPD training. The goal of our methodology is to form the translation competence of a serial translator, so the set of exercises used in the training process is aimed at developing and improving all components of this competence. When teaching PPD through exercises, certain speech skills are mastered. We're talking about message submission and processing actions. about listening in a foreign language and we carry out actions on the formation and creation of TP in a foreign language. We emphasize that we have studied a lot of sources and based on different sources when creating a

set of exercises. To develop our own exercises and improve the set of exercises, the following were used as a basis: the textbook "Interpretation (Economics and Business) – English" (by A. Kuptsova), the scientific "Set of exercises for teaching senior students" article. For consecutive interpretation from a foreign language university" (author O. Zheleznyakova), as well as a guide to translating "The Green Apple" from German to Russian (authors A. Falaleev, A. Malofeeva), the latter provides simultaneous translation is a set of exercises to teach. We also used electronic resources such as sprechpool.net, ted.com, un.org, etc. It should be noted that the set of exercises was created taking into account a number of difficulties that translators usually face during SP. A set of exercises for teaching PPD is organized to overcome these difficulties, as well as according to certain principles. The principle of "mobility" plays a key role in the step-by-step implementation of exercises and the step-by-step implementation, organization and selection of difficulties. The principle of repetition in the organization of language material in exercises, exercises.

1. The principle of step-by-step exercise allows you to overcome the difficulties of PPD individually and consistently. We distinguish preparatory and speech stages of teaching PPD, each of which involves the formation or improvement of certain skills and abilities.

2. In the process of dividing exercises into sections and connecting them with each other, the principle of gradual increase in difficulty is implemented. The preparatory stage consists of four sections of training: formation of listening skills and skills, formation of skills and skills of TP in language design, specific skills and skills of PPD it is necessary to take into account the formation, improvement of previously acquired translation skills and the formation of abilities in different types of PP.

3. The principle of "mobility" in the organization and selection of exercises is implemented in the adjustment of exercises for teaching PAP based on the analysis of inaccuracies made by students when creating TP. This principle makes it possible to identify additional language and speech difficulties that arise in the process of acquiring PPD in students and to introduce additional exercises to eliminate them.

4. The principle of repetition is implemented in the selection of lexical units, phrases and sentences and in the preparation of exercises to improve the skills and competencies of the language design of the translation text (TP). The selection of speech material is organized according to the principle of repetition of the most difficult units for translation, as well as the most important segments of the source text (IT). Thus, during the exercise, students encounter such lexical units several times, which helps to store equivalents of IT structures in memory. PD quality control is carried out during exercises. In addition, students record their translations on a dictaphone. The materials are used to test, analyze, compare and process the results of experimental studies. According to the specifics of PAP implementation, we need to distinguish the stages of mastering PAP and sections of exercises to achieve certain goals at different stages.

Before studying CPD at an advanced level, there should be an introductory theoretical lesson, the purpose of which is to give students a brief overview of the psycholinguistic features of CPD and its components, psychophysiological skills (stress tolerance, volume and clarity). It shows how to achieve the main goal of the course - the implementation of COIN at an advanced level, that is, exercises for teaching PPD and methods for evaluating the performance of exercises by students. In organizing the educational process of PPD, it is possible to distinguish preparation and speech stages. The preparatory stage of teaching PPD, which includes the

elimination of language and psychological difficulties, the development of language and communicative competences, includes the following exercise sections:

- Exercises on improving IT listening skills and qualifications;
- exercises to improve language design skills and competencies of TP;
- Exercises for the formation of special translation skills for the implementation of PAP;
- exercises to improve the translation skills and qualifications formed on the example of the studied types of PD; training them in their practical use.

The speech stage of teaching PAP includes a section of exercises for the formation of specific skills and abilities of PAP, implementation of PAP in different modes. The PPD training course begins with an exercise section to improve IT listening skills and competencies using the example of TV news. Before the work, there will be a discussion on the problem of the lecture. Students express their opinion on the relevant topic, express their opinion on the event under discussion. Such an informal discussion prepares for perception and helps to develop informational and communicative competences, understanding the lecture of a certain topic at the level of the educational text.

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